

pH Metric Studies on the Non-biuret Complex of Copper Succinimide

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Formation of non-biuret complex of succinimide with copper sulphate has been realised below pH 8. pH-metric titrations show that H⁺ ions are released and the anionic form of succinimide takes part in the formation of 1:2 copper succinimide complex. The stepwise and overall stability constants of the complex, calculated by Bjerrum's method, are log $K_1 = 3.5$, log $K_2 = 4.7$, and log $K = 8.2$, where K_1 , K_2 , and K are stability constants for I step, II step, and overall reactions respectively.

In our earlier communication¹, the polarographic behaviour of the violet copper-succinimide complex was discussed. The same method was applied to the study of the blue complex formed in the lower pH range (<8), but no useful information regarding its composition and stability could be obtained in view of the irreversible nature of the reaction. Although conductometric and potentiometric titrations were tried, but the former method failed to provide any inflection point in view of the originally high conductance of the succinimide solution. Similar was the case with spectrophotometric method, since mixtures containing excess of copper sulphate were precipitated, not enabling the use of Job's or slope-ratio method for the determination of the composition of the complex.

EXPERIMENTAL

Succinimide was prepared by the method of Clarke and Behr³ by the action of ammonia on succinic acid and subsequent distillation of the resulting product. Copper sulphate A. R. (B. D. H.) was used for the preparation of 0.1M solution. 0.5M Succinimide solution (20 ml) with 0.4, 0.7, 1.0, 1.3, and 1.6 ml of 0.1M copper sulphate and 1.0 ml of 0.01M-H₂SO₄, making the volume to 25 ml with water, was titrated with 0.1M solution of CO₂-free KOH. All the measurements were performed at 30° ± 0.1°, using a Townsen and Mercer thermostat. pH measurements were made with a Beckman model-G pH-meter with extended electrode leads. The pK value of succinimide was determined from the pH of the half-titration point of the reagent by titrating it against 0.1M-KOH. The value was found to be 9.29

DISCUSSION

To ensure liberation of H⁺ ion during complex-ion formation, pH-metric titrations of mixtures of copper sulphate and succinimide in the ratio of 1:2 and 1:3 against

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1. Khawaja *et al.*, this *Journal*, 1963, **40**, 932.

2. Calvin and Melchori, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, **70**, 3270.

3. "Org. Synthesis", Coll. Vol. II, p. 562.

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As there is no evidence in favour of any one of the above reactions, the composition of this complex can be formulated as $(C_4H_4O_2N)_2 Cu (H_2O)_4$.

The horizontal distance (excess of alkali consumed) between the two curves (Fig. 1) at any value of pH would provide the amount of protons of the acid liberated by complex ion, i.e., the amount of ligand complexed. This value, divided by the total metal ion T_M in the system, afforded the value of $\bar{n}$. Thus at various values of pH, a set of $\bar{n}$ values was determined and the concentration of ligand (A^-) was calculated. The values of $\bar{n}$ were plotted against the corresponding values of pA or $-\log (A^-)$ (Fig. 3). As a first approximation, the values of pA at $\bar{n} = 0.5$ and 1.5 are equal to $\log K_1$ (4.65) and $\log K_2$ (3.6) respectively².

FIG. 3. Degree of formation, $\bar{n}$ as a function of $\log (A^-)$.
 o o-Experimental values.
 x x -Calculated values.

These temporary constants were corrected by Bjerrum's method⁴ of successive approximations. For this case spreading factor, x , introduced by Bjerrum, is given by

$$K_1/K_2 = 4x^2 \text{ or } x = 1.674$$

and formation function is given by

$$\bar{n} = \frac{2 \times k(A^-) + 2 k^2 (A^-)^2}{1 + 2 \times k(A^-) + k^2 (A^-)^2} \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

where k stands for average constant and is given by

$$k = (K_1 K_2)^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

Corrected values of $\bar{n}$, obtained, by solving equation for each corresponding value of (A^-) , were then plotted against $-\log (A^-)$. The final values of $\log K_1$, $\log K_2$, and $\log K$ (overall stability constant) are respectively as 3.5, 4.7, and 8.2.

4. Bjerrum, "Metal Ammine Formation in Aqueous Solution", P. Haas and Son, Copenhagen, 1941.

From the results it is clear that the $\bar{n}$ increases with the increase in pH , showing thereby that it is the anionic form which takes part in the reaction. The behaviour in this pH range is quite different from that of biuret complex of succinimide, as was predicted by polarographic studies. It is also evident from the difference of colour of the two complexes.

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